

DIGITAL PRINTING IN THE PACKAGING INDUSTRY

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Professional paper
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Abstract: *Digital printing is one of the youngest printing techniques. It can be divided into several types, but the most popular are ink jet and electrophotography. Those printing techniques can be used for different products and enable cost-effective short print runs, customization, options, and quick turnaround times, making it a preferred choice for businesses and individuals seeking efficient and on-demand printing solutions.*

Printed products can be divided into publication, commercial printing, and packaging. The packaging group contains labels, cartons, corrugated, flexible, rigid plastics, and metal printing.

The packaging industry plays a vital role in today's global economy. It encompasses various activities in designing, manufacturing, and distributing packaging materials and solutions. Its primary objective is to protect products, ensure safe transportation, and enhance their presentation to consumers.

The packaging industry is a dynamic and essential sector that constantly adapts to meet the evolving demands of businesses and consumers. Its innovations and advancements contribute significantly to the efficient and effective delivery of goods while addressing environmental concerns and enhancing customer experiences.

More packaging printing businesses are now turning to digital printing. It allows for customization, short print runs, and rapid turnaround times, enabling brands to create personalized and targeted packaging designs. With digital printing, companies can achieve vibrant colors, intricate designs, and variable data printing, allowing product differentiation, brand consistency, and enhanced shelf appeal. Additionally, digital printing reduces waste and eliminates the need for

printing plates, making it a more sustainable and cost-effective option for low volume packaging production.

This paper presents the market's current state and predictions for digital printing in the packaging industry.

Keywords: biodegradability, compostability, lignocellulosic material, packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

Printing processes encompass two primary categories: conventional and digital. Conventional printing methods, despite their stark differences, share a common element known as the "printing plate." This printing plate serves as the intermediary for transferring ink onto printing substrates. Within the realm of conventional printing, four prominent techniques emerge: Letterpress, Gravure, Planographic, and Screen Printing (Kipphan, 2001).

Digital printing techniques, on the other hand, dispense with the need for a permanent master. They can be categorized into several groups based on the underlying physical or chemical principles that govern them (Kipphan, 2001). These categories include Electrophotography, Inkjet, Ionography, Magnetography, Thermography, Photography, X-graphy, and others.

Among digital printing methods, Electrophotography and Inkjet stand out as the most widely used techniques for producing a wide array of printed products.

Electrophotography, in particular, involves a series of five essential steps. (Novaković and Kašiković, 2013; Kipphan, 2001; Kašiković, Novaković and Jurič, 2016; Majnarić, 2015):

1. Imaging,
2. Inking,
3. Toner transfer (printing),
4. Toner fixing,
5. Cleaning (conditioning).

Figure 1. Electrophotography.

The inkjet printing process represents a computer-to-print technology wherein ink is dispensed through nozzles. This method eliminates the necessity for a printing master, enabling direct imaging onto the substrate (Kipphan, 2001). This efficiency makes it the swiftest way to imprint information onto a substrate. Within the realm of inkjet printing, two principal groups are prominent: Continuous Inkjet (CIJ) and Drop on Demand Inkjet (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Inkjet technologies.

The primary distinction between these processes lies in how they handle ink droplets. In drop-on-demand inkjet processes, ink droplets are generated only when necessary for the printed information. Conversely, continuous inkjet systems produce a continuous flow of tiny ink droplets, with only a portion

directed onto the substrate based on the image signal. Unprinted droplets are collected and returned for reuse (Soleimani-Gorgani, 2015).

Printed products can be categorized into three primary groups: publications, commercial printing, and packaging (Kasikovic, et al., 2016b). The publication group encompasses newspapers, magazines, books, directories, and catalogues. Commercial printing includes photo products, advertising materials, business forms, identification documents, promotional items, security documents, transactional documents, and general commercial print products. The packaging group consists of labels, cartons, corrugated materials, flexible packaging, rigid plastics, and metal printing.

Notably, the packaging group has been experiencing consistent growth (Kašikovic, et al., 2016a). In contrast, publication volumes and value have seen significant declines, largely due to alternative digital media versions that compete with traditional print products, such as e-books, online publications, electronic media, and social media. Commercial printing witnessed a decline until 2015, with volume remaining stable until 2020 and a slight increase in value (Smith, 2017).

The packaging industry plays a critical role in the global economy by engaging in various activities related to designing, manufacturing, and distributing packaging materials and solutions. Its primary objectives are to protect products, ensure safe transportation, and enhance product presentation to consumers.

The packaging industry is a dynamic and indispensable sector that continually adapts to meet the evolving demands of businesses and consumers. Its innovations and advancements significantly contribute to the efficient and effective delivery of goods while addressing environmental concerns and enhancing customer experiences.

An increasing number of packaging printing businesses are transitioning to digital printing. This shift allows for customization, shorter print runs, and rapid turnaround times, empowering brands to create personalized and targeted packaging designs. Digital printing enables vibrant colors, intricate designs, and variable data printing, fostering product differentiation, brand consistency, and enhanced shelf appeal. Additionally, digital printing reduces waste and eliminates the need for printing plates, making it a more sustainable and cost-effective option for low volume packaging production.

This paper presents an overview of the current state of the market and provides predictions for the future of digital printing in the packaging industry.

2 PACKAGING AND LABELS MARKET

The worldwide print and printed packaging sectors constitute a substantial industry. In 2017, the total revenue from print operations reached nearly \$780 billion, which is equivalent to an astounding 48.73 trillion A4 prints (Smith, 2017).

In terms of constant value, the global market has shown growth since 2012, going from \$749 billion to \$821 billion. However, the overall print volume has declined, dropping from the equivalent of 49.6 trillion A4 prints in 2012 to 48.49 trillion A4 prints in 2022. Looking ahead, there is anticipated growth in real value, but the total print volume continues to decrease. This trend is driven by ongoing changes in product mix, with an increasing emphasis on higher-value items, especially within the packaging sector (Smith, 2017).

From a macroeconomic perspective, the situation appears generally favorable. However, this masks the diverse prospects for various product categories, printing processes, and regional markets.

2. 1 Printed packaging market

In addition to non-printed packaging materials like glass, films, and plain boxes, printed packaging encompasses various forms, including corrugated packaging, cartons/sleeves, flexible packaging, rigid plastics, and metal containers. Printing on packaging serves a dual purpose by not only promoting the product to potential buyers but also offering essential information about its contents. On a global scale, the packaging industry is experiencing growth, driven by increasing populations, the shift from agriculture to industrialization, and the ongoing trend of urbanization. Packaging plays a pivotal role in enabling efficient supply chains, ensuring that a diverse array of products reaches markets worldwide (Smith, 2017).

Each of these packaging categories has numerous driving factors, enhancing choices and convenience while optimizing supply chain operations. The choice of printing methods varies across regions. In North America, flexography (Flexo) dominates corrugated and flexible packaging, whereas in Asia, gravure takes precedence. This is due to quality-conscious Japanese packaging converters who initially faced challenges in achieving the desired quality with flexo, especially for printing kanji text characters, before durable plates became available. The digital print sector is rapidly evolving, and inkjet technology is expected to make significant advancements until 2022, particularly in corrugated packaging, cartons, flexible packaging, and direct-to-shape printing (Smith, 2017).

Over a ten-year period, printed packaging output is projected to grow by 34.4% in real terms, excluding the effects of inflation. In volume terms, this growth is estimated to reach 36.4%. By 2022, the total output will be slightly less than the equivalent of 10 trillion A4 prints. Packaging represented 44.8% of the total value of all printing activities in 2012, a figure represented rise to 55.9% in 2022. This underscores the increasing significance of packaging within the broader printing industry, although in terms of volume, it remains a smaller segment, accounting for 16.5% in 2012 and 23.6% in 2022.

2. 2 Labels market

Product labels serve the dual purpose of conveying essential information about a product's contents and enticing potential users to engage with the item. These labels also maintain their importance throughout the lifespan of the product, catering to end consumers, including households and workplaces. In certain contexts, such as pharmaceuticals in dispensaries or hospitals, the information on labels can be of critical significance (Smith, 2017).

Printed labels come in various forms, including wet-glued labels, pressure-sensitive labels, shrink and stretch sleeves, or in-mould labels. Additionally, there is a substantial sector dedicated to multi-part tracking labels utilized in logistics and supply chain management.

In the realm of litho printed paper labels and in-mould labels, narrow-web flexo presses dominate, especially in the pressure-sensitive (self-adhesive) category where labels are applied by machines at high speeds. Digital printing has made substantial inroads into the label market, particularly through electrophotography, with HP Indigo leading the market, followed closely by Xeikon, as well as numerous manufacturers of narrow-web inkjet presses. Xeikon, for instance, introduced its first inkjet machine in 2017 and subsequently acquired the EFI Jetrion business in October 2017, more than a decade after its parent company, Flint, had sold Jetrion to EFI (Smith, 2017).

In 2017, global revenues from printed labels amounted to slightly less than \$37.0 billion. The market is projected to grow at an average Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 4.1% through 2022 in terms of value. Simultaneously, the print volume is increased from 856 billion A4-sized sheets in 2012 to over 1.42 trillion A4 sheets in 2022, marking a growth of two-thirds within a decade (Smith, 2017).

2. 3 Digital printing in packaging and labels market

In table 1 and 2 are presented digital printing processes used in global packaging and label market (Smith, 2017).

Table 1. Digital printing processes used in global packaging printing market, 2012–22.

\$ million	2012	2022	CAGR (%) 2017–22
<i>total</i>	307,475.50	413,552.10	3.1
<i>Electrophotography</i>	56.20	1,568.20	22.5
<i>Inkjet</i>	1,035.40	7,312.50	26.3
Billion A4 prints	2012	2022	CAGR (%) 2017–22
<i>total</i>	7,331,658	9,998,829	3.5
<i>Electrophotography</i>	309	11,721	21.9
<i>Inkjet</i>	4,417	96,876	39.4

In Table 1, we observe the utilization of digital printing processes within the global packaging printing market output, spanning the years 2012 to 2022, presented in millions of dollars (adjusted for constant 2016 prices and exchange rates). The data illustrates a substantial increase in these processes during this period (Smith, 2017).

Specifically, in the realm of electrophotography, the market value has surged from \$56.2 million in 2012 to \$1,568.2 million in 2022, accounting for less than 1% of the market's total value. Meanwhile, inkjet technology has experienced remarkable growth, escalating from \$1,035.4 million in 2012 to \$7,312.5 million in 2022, albeit still representing less than 2% of the market's overall value.

Throughout the 2012-2022 timeframe, print volumes have also demonstrated significant growth. Electrophotography contributed to this increase, albeit to a smaller extent, with print volumes rising from 309 billion A4-sized sheets to 11,721 billion A4-sized sheets, which constitutes just 0.11% of the total print volume. In contrast, inkjet technology has seen substantial growth, with print volumes surging from 4,417 billion A4-sized sheets in 2012 to an impressive 96,876 billion A4-sized sheets in 2022, albeit still representing less than 1% of the total print volume.

In Table 2, we examine the application of digital printing processes within the global label printing market output from 2012 to 2022. The figures are presented in millions of dollars, adjusted for constant 2016 prices and exchange rates. The data highlights a significant expansion of these digital printing methods during this time frame (Smith, 2017)..

Table 2. Digital printing processes used in global label printing market, 2012–22.

\$ million	2012	2022	CAGR (%) 2017–22
<i>total</i>	28,166.10	45,220.90	4.1
<i>Electrophotography</i>	4,705.60	7,596.20	2.8
<i>Inkjet</i>	1,054.80	6,705.80	13.3
Billion A4 prints	2012	2022	CAGR (%) 2017–22
<i>total</i>	855,632	1,425,072	5.5

<i>Electrophotography</i>	49,416	96,994	5.2
<i>Inkjet</i>	10,846	100,258	17.5

Specifically, in the domain of electrophotography, the market value has surged from \$4,705.62 million in 2012 to \$7,596.2 million in 2022, constituting just under 17% of the market's total value. On the other hand, inkjet technology has witnessed remarkable growth, escalating from \$1,054.8 million in 2012 to \$6,705.8 million in 2022, although it still represents slightly less than 15% of the market's overall value.

Throughout the 2012-2022 period, print volumes have also shown substantial growth. Electrophotography has contributed to this increase, albeit to a lesser extent, with print volumes rising from 49,416 billion A4-sized sheets to 96,994 billion A4-sized sheets, making up approximately 6.8% of the total print volume. In contrast, inkjet technology has experienced significant growth, with print volumes surging from 10,846 billion A4-sized sheets in 2012 to an impressive 100,258 billion A4-sized sheets in 2022, representing more than 7% of the total print volume.

3 DIGITAL PRINTING FOR PACKAGING AND LABEL APPLICATIONS

The evolution of digital printing technology for packaging applications continues to drive progress, offering increased production flexibility and unleashing creativity in packaging design. This innovation benefits not only converters but also brand owners who engage in on-demand printing and labeling.

The digital printing packaging market is categorized into Packaging Type, Printing Technology, and End-User Industry. In terms of printing inks, the market is segmented into UV-based inks, solvent-based inks, and dye sublimation inks. Printing technology covers inkjet printing, electro photography, magnetography, and thermal printing. Packaging types include folding cartons, corrugated, labels, flexible packaging, and others. End-user industries encompass food & beverages, automotive, pharmaceuticals, and others. Geographically, the global digital printing packaging market analysis spans North America (including the U.S., Canada, and Mexico), Europe (comprising the UK, France, Germany, Italy, and the rest of Europe), Asia-Pacific (encompassing China, Japan, India, South Korea, and the rest of Asia-Pacific), and LAMEA (encompassing Latin America, the Middle East, and Africa). (<https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/digital-printing-packaging-market-A08308>)

Assessing packaging types, labels commanded over two-thirds of the global digital printing packaging market in 2021 and are anticipated to retain their market dominance until 2031. During the same period, the flexible packaging segment is poised for significant growth in adopting digital printing. – (<https://www.packagingdigest.com/digital-printing/whats-happening-digital-printing-packaging>)

Food and beverages constitute two major categories for digitally printed packaging, exemplifying the seamless fit of digital printing, particularly for craft and artisanal consumables. For companies in the consumer goods sector, digital printing technology delivers high-quality packaging while unlocking the benefits of small production runs, personalized packaging, waste reduction, swift turnaround times, and the capacity for real-time modifications to packaging designs.

In the pharmaceuticals and cannabis industries, brand owners are increasingly turning to digital printing to address the need for localized packaging, legally mandated variable data, and agile, frequent design adjustments. Advancements in equipment expand the range of packaging materials and formats amenable to digital printing, spanning from aluminum beverage cans to food wrappers and metallized-film pouches. Furthermore, a broader array of digitally printed embellishments is now within reach, including raised finishes, spot coating, digital foiling, and metallic inks.

3. 1 Digital printing examples in packaging and label industry

European pharmaceutical reimporters are uncovering a multitude of advantages by taking label printing activities under their own roof. Notably, digital printing has emerged as a solution that effectively tackles numerous challenges for these enterprises, which specialize in repackaging medications for distribution across countries within the European Economic Area (<https://www.packagingdigest.com/digital-printing/whats-happening-digital-printing-packaging>).

The labels on pharmaceutical products must continuously adapt to cater to diverse factors, including local regulatory demands, multiple languages, and variable information such as expiry dates, lot numbers, and track-and-trace codes. Additionally, these labels frequently require the incorporation of printed anti-counterfeit features.

Furthermore, pharmaceutical reimporters encounter fluctuating print run sizes, with some runs comprising as few as 50 labels. Digital printing's ability to handle variable data and accommodate short print runs positions it as a highly prized in-

house technology for these companies (<https://www.packagingdigest.com/digital-printing/whats-happening-digital-printing-packaging>).

Figure 3. In-house printing streamlines drug labeling.

Colordruck Baiersbronn, a packaging producer and printer, harnessed the power of digital printing to craft 40 distinctive candy boxes for participants attending an annual gathering of esteemed confectioners in Switzerland (<https://www.packagingdigest.com/digital-printing/whats-happening-digital-printing-packaging>).

Within each of these meticulously crafted boxes lies a handcrafted praline, encased in a cube-shaped paper wrapper adorned with a unique image of a majestic mountain peak. To achieve this diversity of prints on the wrappers, the printer employed HP SmartStream Mosaic digital printing software, capable of generating countless variations of images.

Colordruck went a step further by creating vibrant, sizeable prints to grace the inside of the box lids. Each box featured a distinct image, ensuring a unique experience for each recipient. The exterior of the box top featured small, abstract alpine images, serving as a preview of the imagery found on the wrappers. These miniature representations were also created using digital printing techniques.

To add a personalized touch, the converter incorporated the recipient's name and event details through digital foiling on the top of the box.

Figure 4. Digital foiling personalizes chocolate boxes.

Sealed Air, now operating under the name SEE, is fully embracing digital technology with the introduction of its prismatic digital packaging brand. The prismatic digital printers cater to the requirements of both converters and brand owners who handle their own printing. These technologies place a particular emphasis on flexible packaging for food.

SEE utilizes its large-format prismatic 5540 digital printer to provide customers with digitally printed flexible packaging. This wide-format system excels in high-speed, full-color, photographic-quality printing and is compatible with metallic and invisible inks (<https://www.packagingdigest.com/digital-printing/whats-happening-digital-printing-packaging>).

The range of materials the 5540 printer can work with includes rollstock plastic films, shrink bags, mailers, and fiber-based packaging. Notably, it can print on both sides of packaging materials, accomplishing this automatically through the use of a turn bar in the press.

The prismatic product line also encompasses small-format digital printers that brand owners can integrate into their packaging lines, resulting in retail-ready packages. Some of these systems are significantly smaller, with a size that's just one-tenth of conventional presses.

Currently, SEE is conducting tests of the small printers with ecommerce and food-protein brand owners. Potential applications include personalized, on-demand packaging featuring unique images, messages, and codes. The company aims to make some of these smaller systems commercially available in early 2023.

Figure 5. Prismiq digital packaging brand.

The landscape of digital printing solutions for beverage companies, especially craft producers, is expanding as digital can printing becomes more accessible. This technology offers a range of advantages for small to midsize brand owners, including the ability to produce small print runs, quick changeovers, and cost-effective limited-edition and personalized packaging.

Furthermore, direct-to-can digital printing offers environmental benefits by eliminating the need for labels on cans. Craft brands adopting this approach make their packaging significantly more recyclable (<https://www.packagingdigest.com/digital-printing/whats-happening-digital-printing-packaging>).

Craft Canning + Printing, a subsidiary of Eastside Distilling based in Portland, Oregon, has recently installed a German-made Hinterkopf D240.2 digital can printer to cater to this segment of the beverage market. The D240.2 model boasts an impressive print resolution of up to 1,200 dots per inch, enabling the system to generate photorealistic images with seamless ink coverage. This printer excels at producing fine gradients, subtle shading, and crisp text and edges.

Notably, Craft Canning + Printing has set a minimum order requirement of 400 cans, available in either 12- or 16-ounce volumes. By offering digital can printing with such a low minimum order quantity, they have made it a viable option for small beer, wine, and cider companies, granting them access to professional-looking, sustainable packaging solutions.

Figure 6. Digital can printing.

4 CONCLUSION

The label and packaging industry is poised for a transformative evolution, with digital printing at the forefront of this paradigm shift. Through a comprehensive review of current trends and emerging technologies, it is evident that the future of digital printing in this industry holds immense promise and potential.

Customization and Personalization: Digital printing enables the production of labels and packaging with unprecedented levels of customization and personalization. As consumer preferences continue to diversify, brands will increasingly turn to digital printing to create unique and tailored packaging solutions that resonate with their target audiences.

Short-Run Flexibility: The agility offered by digital printing in accommodating short print runs and quick changeovers is paramount. This flexibility allows brands to respond swiftly to market demands, reduce waste, and optimize inventory management, ultimately leading to cost savings and improved sustainability.

Advanced Printing Technologies: Advancements in inkjet and electrophotography technologies are enhancing the quality and speed of digital printing. High-resolution, photorealistic graphics, intricate designs, and vibrant colors are becoming standard features, further blurring the line between digital and traditional printing methods.

Sustainability and Eco-Friendliness: The elimination of traditional label substrates, such as adhesive-backed paper, in favor of eco-friendly alternatives is a growing trend. Digital printing's reduced waste, minimal setup requirements,

and compatibility with recyclable materials position it as an eco-conscious choice in the label and packaging industry.

Smart Packaging Integration: Digital printing can seamlessly incorporate smart packaging elements like QR codes, NFC tags, and augmented reality features. This convergence of digital and physical realms enhances consumer engagement, product traceability, and brand-consumer interactions.

Industry 4.0 Integration: The integration of digital printing with Industry 4.0 technologies, such as IoT-enabled machinery and AI-driven production optimization, will further streamline production processes, minimize downtime, and maximize efficiency.

Market Expansion: Digital printing is breaking down barriers in terms of market access, making it a viable option for smaller businesses and niche markets. The reduced barriers to entry will democratize the label and packaging industry, fostering innovation and competition.

In conclusion, the future of digital printing in the label and packaging industry is one marked by innovation, sustainability, and adaptability. As technology continues to advance and consumer expectations evolve, digital printing will play a pivotal role in enabling brands to differentiate themselves in a crowded marketplace. Embracing digital printing not only offers operational efficiencies but also opens up new avenues for creativity and customer engagement. As a result, it is imperative for industry stakeholders to invest in digital printing technologies and stay at the forefront of this transformative journey. The label and packaging industry stands on the brink of a digital renaissance, and those who embrace it will shape the future landscape of this dynamic and evolving sector.

Acknowledgments: *This paper has been supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation through project no. 451-03-47/2023-01/200156 “Innovative scientific and artistic research from the FTS (activity) domain”.*

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